

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF COPOLYMERS OF EPOXY RESIN AND DEPOLYMERIZATE OF POLYURETHANE

Han Na Kim, Nguyen Dinh Huong, Dai Soo. Lee*

*Division of Semiconductor and Chemical Engineering,
Chonbuk National University, Deokjin-dong 664-14, Jeonju 561-756, Korea,*

E-mail: daisoolee@chonbuk.ac.kr

Keywords: *composite polymer recycling*

1 Introduction

Polymer matrix reinforced by woven fabrics is probably the most commonly used form of composites in structural application such as aircrafts, boats, and automobiles, etc. [1]. The fiber reinforced polyurethane (PU) are being used for high performance composites due to their light weight and superior heat insulation as well as good mechanical characteristics.

The high versatility of polyurethane allows to produce a large variety of products with structures which may range from liner and flexible to highly cross-linked and rigid, and capable of satisfying various application requirements [2]. Since a large quantity of waste foams have been discharged in the various stages of manufacture, processing, and after usage, it is becoming necessary for them to be treated or recycled [3]. Glycolysis is a comparatively simple process in which diols are used to convert polyurethanes into a liquid regenerate at about 200°C under ambient pressure and the most widely used for chemical recycling method for PU, both for rigid PU and flexible PU. The aim is generally the recovery of polyols for the production of new PU material from various PU composites [4].

Epoxy resins have been widely used for adhesives, constructions, coatings, and electronic devices due to their excellent mechanical and thermal properties. But their brittleness sometimes limited further applications. So, toughening of epoxy resins has been attracting attentions of researchers in industries and academia. Frequently, elastomeric impact modifiers are being incorporated into epoxy resins to improve toughness of the resins after cure.

Cationic polymerization can lead to a crosslinking process if diepoxides are taken as monomer. Thus, a wide variety of compounds such as $AlCl_3$, $SnCl_4$, $TiCl_4$, $SbCl_5$ or BF_3 can be used as catalyst of

cationic curing of epoxy resins, featuring a fast cure rate [5]. Boron trifluorides was used as the Lewis acid. The most readily available complex is boron trifluoride etherate [6]. In this paper, we investigated cationic copolymerization of epoxy resins with depolymerizate of PU foam based on poly(propylene glycol)s to introduce flexible segments into crosslinked structure after the cure of epoxy resins. The PU foam is one of typical matrix of fiber reinforced composites for insulation.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and sample preparation

2.1.1. Materials

The following chemicals were used for depolymerization: scraps of semi-rigid polyurethane foam provided by a local PU foam manufacturer. Diethylene glycol (DEG) and titanium butoxide were used as received from Aldrich Chemical. For the copolymerization, two types of polyol (poly propylene glycol (PPG) from Kumho Petrochemical, PPG400 (diol, $M_w=400g/mol$) and PPG2070 (triol, $M_w=672g/mol$), and bisphenol-A epoxy resin (YD-128, EEW:187g/eq), from Kukdo Chemical in Korea were used. Boron trifluoride diethyletherate was used as the cationic catalyst.

2.1.2. Glycolysis of PU scraps

When polyurethane is reacted with diols at temperatures above 200°C and depolymerizations proceeds fast, via glycolysis. Glycolysis includes the heat-up of pre-grinded PU scrap for several hours, preferably waste PU foam to 200°C in high boiling point glycol with the titanium butoxide chosen as a

catalyst and the maintaining the system for 6 hours at 200°C.

2.1.3 Copolymerization

The copolymer of depolymerizate which was obtained by depolymerization of PU scrap by glycolysis and epoxy resin was relatively brittle because of the high cross linking density. So we added additional polyol for the control of mechanical property. The codes of samples are given in Table 1. The catalyst added was 2 phr. And the mixture was cured at 100°C in Teflon mold.

2.2. Measurement

IR spectra were recorded with an FT-IR spectrometer (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy: FT-IR, JASCO FT/IR-300E). The T_g s of the copolymers were measured by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, TA Q-20)

at a heating speed of 10°C/min. The mechanical properties of the cured samples were measured by Universal Testing Machine (UTM, LLOYD co. AMETEK) according to ASTM D638. The tension speed was 50 mm/min at constant temperature. We obtained average value from the measurements of five specimens for each sample.

Table1. Sample codes and formulation of copolymers from the epoxy resin and depolymerizate of polyurethane scraps

Sample code	Composition of binder (molar ratio)			
	Epoxy resin	Depolymerizate	PPG-400	PPG-2070
A-1	1	0.5	0.40	0.10
A-2	1	0.5	0.25	0.25
A-3	1	0.5	0.10	0.40
B-1	1	0.4	0.50	0.10
B-2	1	0.4	0.30	0.30
B-3	1	0.4	0.10	0.50

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Cationic curing of the epoxy resin

Figure1. FTIR spectra of PPG (a), depolymerizate (b), YD-128 (c), mixture of sample before (d) and after cure (e) at 100°C.

Figure 1 shows the FTIR spectra of raw materials and the copolymer formed after cure. The appearance of the band between 950 cm^{-1} and 815 cm^{-1} was attributed to epoxy. The infrared spectrum of YD-128 (c) and mixture of sample before cure (d) are compared with the spectrum of cured sample (e). It was observed the characteristic epoxy peak at 915 cm^{-1} disappeared in cured sample because of the epoxy ring-opening polymerization.

3.2 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the copolymers are given in Figure 2 and summarized in Table 2. To study the effects of depolymerizate, contents of the depolymerizate were varied in the A-series and the B-series.

Lowering the depolymerizate content in B-series resulted in the increase of elongation at break but showed decrease of tensile strength. As the depolymerizate of rigid PU foam contained polyols of high functionality,

Figure 2. UTM data of copolymers with different contents of depolymerizate and PPG functionality.

Table 2. Tensile properties of the copolymers from epoxy/polyol

Sample code	Tensile strength (Mpa)	Elongation at break (%)
A-1	13.4	168
A-2	15.7	159
A-3	16.6	155
B-1	5.1	210
B-2	5.6	171
B-3	6.0	162

copolymers prepared from A-series containing more depolymerizate, become relatively brittle. And the copolymers of increased diol (PPG-400) content showed increase of elongation at break but decrease of tensile strength. Can be attributed to the lower cross-linking density of the hybrids due to low functionality constituents of the hybrids. Moduli of the samples after cure increased by the incorporation of depolymerizate or PPG triol because of the increased crosslink density.

3.3 Thermal properties

Figure 3 shows the dynamic DSC thermograms obtained for epoxy and polyol initiated with BF_3 - as cationic catalyst. Table 3 shows the thermal properties of the copolymers. As can be seen, there is great dependence of the maximum exotherm temperatures (T_{max}) and heat of cure (ΔH) on the proportion of polyol type.

The T_{max} is increased and ΔH is decreased with the molecular weight and the total amount of polyol in the mixtures [7]. Due to the decreased epoxy contents resulted in low ΔH s of ring opening of epoxy resin. But the T_{max} increased with increasing the depolymerizate content, getting small molecular weight. Due to the depolymerizate have low reactivity than PPG.

Table 3. Thermal properties of epoxy/polyol copolymers

Sample code	T_{max} (°C)	ΔH (cal/g)	T_g (°C)
A-1	112.24	60.43	-5.15
A-2	116.19	58.28	-4.81
A-3	117.93	60.83	-4.19
B-1	90.37	59.97	-10.5
B-2	93.90	54.97	-9.53
B-3	82.62	54.34	-7.62

Figure 3. DSC thermograms of copolymers with different contents of depolymerizate and PPG functionality.

(a) & (c) were obtained by 1st scan and (b) & (d) were by 2nd scan.

The exothermic peaks disappear in the second scan (Figure 3 (b), (d)). The polymers displayed glass transitions near 0°C. These lower values of glass transition temperature could be due to the presence of PPG [8]. The crosslink density increased with increasing depolymerizate and triol, they have many functionality. So, which was evident from the increasing Tg.

Acknowledgements

It is acknowledged that this work was supported by National Research Foundation through the Human Resource Training Project for Regional Innovation and Ministry of Environment through 2010 Environmental Technology Development Project.

References

- [1] Suhreta Husic, Lvan Javni, Zoran S. Petrovic, *Composites Science and Technology*, 65, 19 (2005).
- [2] Shutov, F., Mechanical Recycling of Polyurethane Scrap, in *Recycling of Polyurethanes*, Chapter 3, pp 43-119, Edited by Frish, K. C., Klempner, D. and prentice, G., Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, 1999.
- [3] Hayashi. F., General Purpose Adhesives Prepared from Chemically Recycled Waste Rigid Polyurethans Foams, in *Recycling of Polyurethanes*, Chapter 6, pp 223-240, Edited by Frish, K. C., Klempner, D. and prentice, G., Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, 1999.
- [4] Alliance for the Polyurethanes Industry. <<http://www.polyurethane.org/recycling>>.

- [5] May CA., Epoxy resins, Chemical and Technology, New York, Marcel Dekker, 1988.
- [6] C. S. Chen and E. M. Pearce, *J. Appl. Ploy. Sci.*, 37, 1105, 1989.
- [7] A. Hartwig, K. Koschek, *Polymer*, 44, 2853, 2003.
- [8] A. J. Ryan, U. R. Vaidya. *Polymer Bulletin*, 24, 521, 1990.